

MODELLING OF DAMAGE AND SCALING EFFECTS IN COMPOSITE PIPES SUBJECTED TO LOW-VELOCITY IMPACTS.

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Keywords: Composite pipes, impact, damage, finite elements.

ABSTRACT

Even though composite pipes present important advantages for the oil and gas industry as a high resistance to corrosion or a good strength–weight relationship, its implementation has been restrained by the difficulty to predict their behaviour when affected by transversal impacts, which cause damage that can be difficult to detect. The present work aims to develop a simulation tool to model the damage caused low-velocity impact and try to establish a relationship with the geometry of the pipe, focusing in three of the pipe parameters: diameter, length and thickness.

A model with these characteristics would anticipate the appropriate dimensions of the pipe needed for satisfying specific necessities required by the pipeline design. By increasing the confidence in the modelling of composite structures, the long process of testing every variation in the geometric properties of the pipe will be significantly reduced and the use of composite pipes will increase.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of composite pipes has become widely spread in the oil and gas industry over the last years. They are suitable for the transportation of fluid materials such as gas, oil and all types of water and they can be used both underground and underwater due to the high resistance to corrosion that the material provides. The main challenge that these pipes face is their high sensitivity to transverse loading, as for example the drop of a tool, due to the lack of fibres in the thickness direction. The area damaged by the impact, which sometimes is not possible to be detected, suffers a loss of properties and that can cause a premature failure of the structure. The understanding of the damage mechanisms and the possibility of developing a model to predict the results of impact for different values of the pipe geometric parameters as for example length, diameter and thickness, will save companies the economic and time costs of studying every model of pipe used.

2 REVIEW OF DAMAGE AND FAILURE IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Damage can be defined as the degradation of the material properties while failure is the incapability of the material to perform for the task for which it was designed. That means that a damaged material can perform until it fails, even though its properties are not the initial ones. Failure can happen instantly or it can be a consequence of the growth and propagation of damage.

2.1 Failure

Failure starts at the micro-structural level, where the state of stress causes micro failures that coalesce and form the macro-damage. Since it is very complicated to localize the micro damage, only the global behaviour of the lamina can be approximated.

The first failure theories applied to composite materials were adaptations of the ones used for ductile materials, such as Maximum Stress, Maximum Strain and Tsai-Wu. Later on, specific models for composite materials were developed [1] being the Hashin criterion [2, 3] one of the most used due to the good agreement with the experimental results. It is strength-stress based and contemplates two different failure modes, fibre and matrix, with two different types of load, tension and compression.

2.2 Damage

Damage modes are usually classified into two groups: intralaminar and interlaminar. Intralaminar modes are the ones initiated and developed in the lamina and the most common ones are matrix cracking and fibre interface failure. The interlaminar damage modes are those that happen in the interface of two adjacent plies. The principal mode is called delamination and it causes the plies to separate, with the consequent loss of strength of the laminate.

2.2.1 Intralaminar damage

Matrix cracking is the most abundant and first failure mode in the majority of the cases [4-6]. It triggers other damage modes such as delamination or fibre-matrix debonding and also leads to fibre failure. The study of the effects of matrix cracking in composites and the development of models to describe the stress distribution is one of the most important topics in the research field.

One of the models used to calculate the stiffness of the cracked lamina is the known as Ply Discount model. It consists in reducing the properties of the material (Young's modulus, shear modulus and/or Poisson's ratios) when failure is detected [7, 8].

Regarding the damage propagation, a popular approach is the Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) [9-13]. CDM expresses the mechanical properties of the material as a function of damage, which is represented as an internal state variable, and then compares the values of stress and strain obtained throughout the damage evolution with the critical values of the material.

2.2.2 Interlaminar damage

Delamination is the main interlaminar damage mode. It is caused by high interlaminar stresses that separate the plies and causes important losses of laminate stiffness. The study of delamination is usually approached by two different methods, the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) and the Cohesive Zone Model (CZM).

The VCCT assumes that the energy released during the delamination in a certain length is equal to the work required to close the crack to its original length while the external load remains present and unchanged [34]. The delamination growth is predicted when a combination of the components of the energy release rate is equal to a critical value.

The CZM models the coalescence of crazes in the resinous layer at the tip of the crack and represents the way in which the material loses its load-carrying capacity [14]. The CZM is based on the relationship between tractions (τ) and displacement jumps (Δ) in the interface where the crack may occur. When the area under the τ - Δ curve is equal to the fracture toughness, the traction is reduced to zero and new crack surfaces are formed. The crack propagation directions are those that maximize the energy release rate. The path of propagation is restricted to a surface known beforehand, which is modeled as an adhesive interface [15]. The main advantages of the CZM,

which have made them preferred over VCCT, are that it can predict both the crack initiation and propagation and that it does not rely on the existence of a previous crack.

3 SCALE AND SIZE EFFECTS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

As stated before, the main objective in this study is to develop a model able to simulate the effect of low-velocity impact in composite pipes and to anticipate failure independently of the dimensions of the pipe.

Following this purpose, Tarfaoui *et al* [16] developed an experimental study which purpose was to determine if it was possible to substitute the study of real size pipes by smaller ones. The proportionality rule followed was to maintain constant the Cauchy number, which relates the density, the velocity, and the Young's modulus of the structure. The results obtained showed that the scaling laws got good results for contact time and the displacement of the impacted area but that they were not so good for the damage development. The internal stresses were considered as the cause for the disagreement in the damage development and the origin of these stresses was attributed to local variations of the composition of the pipe, such as the fiber distribution or cure gradients. The tests developed by Davies and Petton [17], who also studied the possibility of using smaller specimens to predict the behavior of composite materials, concluded that it is possible to calculate the in-plane elastic constants and strength data if the small specimen recreates exactly the bigger ones.

One of the classic approaches to the problem is the dimensional analysis, based in the Buckingham's Pi-theorem [18], which consists on grouping the variables of the problem in sets of non-dimensional parameters that can be compared between different sizes of the model. Hafeez and Almaskari [19] followed these precepts to develop an experimental study where certain parameters of the experiment such as the diameter, thickness, length, radius of the indenter and number of layers of the different pipes followed certain relations so that the results could be compared to each other.

4 METHODOLOGY

The model used for the simulation is based on Li's continuum damage model [20], which was further validated by Almaskari [21]. This model accounts for three sources of nonlinearity during the analysis of the laminate: the plastic shear stress-strain relation, the fibre reorientation and transverse matrix cracking. The model is focused on matrix cracking due to its importance in the damage development. Its effects are represented by a damage parameter, ω , which is defined as the relative change of the transverse Young's Modulus:

$$\omega = 1 - \frac{E_2}{E_2^0} \quad (1)$$

The resultant reduced stiffness matrix is given by:

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_1^0}{1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0} & \frac{\nu_{12}^0 E_2^0}{1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{12}^0 E_2^0}{1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0} & \frac{E_2^0}{1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & kG_\epsilon \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0 E_1^0}{(1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0)^2} & -\frac{\nu_{12}^0 E_2^0}{(1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0)^2} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}^0 E_2^0}{(1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0)^2} & -\frac{E_2^0}{(1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0)^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & kG_\epsilon \end{bmatrix} \omega \quad (2)$$

The damage parameter varies depending on the load applied and is recorded during the analysis as a Solution Dependent Variable (SDV).

Failure is modelled with the Ply Discount model. It contemplates three different types of intra-laminar damage: matrix cracking, fibre breakage and nonlinear shear. Hashin criterion will be used to account for failure.

The implementation of the interlaminar damage is still on progress and it will include the CZM introduced in Section 2.2.2.

Due to the similar results of low-speed impact and quasi-static indentation [22], the problem is going to be modelled as quasi-static indentation in ABAQUS through UMAT, an user subroutine that allows to customize the material response of the problem. UMAT takes as inputs from ABAQUS the material properties constants and an approximate value of the strain increments and then it calculates the laminar stiffness, determines the increment of plastic shear strain and predicts the total stresses which are then returned to ABAQUS for an equilibrium check.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The studied problem consists on a cylindrical GRE tube with variable diameters, lengths and number of layers, all of them of $\pm 55^\circ$ and a thickness of 0.25 mm. The indenter is a rigid hemisphere with a diameter of 50 mm placed at the top center of the tube. The total displacement of the indenter is 50 mm, applied in increments of 0.5 mm. The tube is supported by a rigid plate and it is modeled with 4-noded shell elements with reduced integration (S4R) and a friction coefficient between the parts of 0.1. The complete composition can be seen in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Problem composition.

The initial material properties of the E-glass fibre are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Ply material properties of the E-glass.

Engineering constant		
E_1	[GPa]	45.6
E_2	[GPa]	16.2
ν_{12}	–	0.278
G_{12}	[GPa]	5.5
G_{13}	[GPa]	5.5
G_{21}	[GPa]	5.5
X_t	[MPa]	1280
X_c	[MPa]	525
Y_t	[MPa]	40
Y_c	[MPa]	145
X_t	[MPa]	1280
S_{12}	[MPa]	73

There are three models for each of the geometrical aspects studied: the basic or unit (model 1), one with the size of the parameter doubled and one tripled. The amount of models has been considered sufficient as a first approach to get a general overview of the problem but more sizes should be included in further studies. It is also important to notice that the graphs that are going to be displayed show the reaction force (RF) against the indentation level. This is because the RF represents the response of the whole structure and it is easy to compare these graphs with experimental results.

5.1 Influence of the diameter

The results of models 1, 2 and 3 are compared and shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Parametric study: diameter.

There is a remarkable difference between the results of model 1 and the results of models 2 and 3, that diminishes when increasing the indentation level. As explained in [16], this is caused by the fact that bigger pipes are able to absorb a higher amount of energy elastically by getting deformed, so they suffer a lower amount of damage due to the lower stiffness. Another cause for these

differences is the depth of the indentation, for model 1 it accounts for the 50% of the diameter, whereas for model 2 is the 25% and for model 3 is just the 17%.

5.2 Influence of the thickness

The results of models 1, 4 and 5 are compared and shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that there is a direct relationship between the thickness and the stiffness of the pipes. In comparison with model 1, model 4 has a reaction force seven times bigger and model 5, around twenty. These relationships keep pretty much constant for all the indentation although it slightly diminishes with its progress.

Figure 3. Parametric study: thickness.

As explained in [16], in this case the damage of the pipe increases with the thickness because of the higher number of interfaces. If the thickness of the pipe had been increased by increasing the thickness of the layers, the situation would have been different.

It is important to notice that there is no complete data of models 4 and 5 cases due to premature divergence of the simulation model.

5.3 Influence of the thickness

The results of models 1, 6 and 7 are compared and shown in Figure 4. As can be seen in the graph, the results of model 6 and 7 are very close, with a small anticipation of the damage by the longest pipe which can be caused by the fact that the storage energy increases with the length of the specimen [23].

Model 1 differs noticeably from models 6 and 7 by getting lower values of the reaction force and consequently lower stiffness, for the same indentation value. This can be explained by the fact that the reaction force is a global parameter that accounts for the results that happen all along the pipe. Since the pipe is shorter, there is less material to counteract the effects of the indentation. However, there is not a clear relationship between the increase of the length and the increase of the stiffness but it can be concluded that there is one value of the length at which its effects are no longer remarkable in the behavior of the pipe. A higher number of models are needed in this case to understand better the effect of the length.

Figure 4. Parametric study: length.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A parametric study of three geometrical parameters of GRE pipes under quasi-static indentation has been developed. For that, a simulation model which includes the damage and failure caused by intralaminar damage modes has been implemented in ABAQUS through a UMAT subroutine.

The trends of the results, which compare well with conclusions from other publications, show a direct relationship between the increase of the diameter and the thickness and the increase of the reaction force for same levels of indentation. While this relationship is clear and almost constant for the thickness, it varies depending on the level of indentation for the diameter. Regarding the length, the difference between the models becomes less important for the longer models, which indicates that there is a limit length from which the length effects almost disappear. The study of a higher number of models seems necessary for a better understanding of the problem.

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